

Strategy 2016 - 2018

We protect consumers by leading a collaborative food safety community to continuously raise food standards and create a culture of excellence

Foreword

A healthy population with access to safe food and the ability to make informed choices about the food it eats is the foundation of a healthy society and a fully functioning economy. Irish society and the Irish economy benefit significantly from a growing food industry which produces and manufactures food for the domestic and export markets. And it is the Food Safety Authority of Ireland's (FSAI) responsibility, as Ireland's independent science-based regulatory enforcement agency for food safety, to protect consumers. We will do this by leading a collaborative food safety community, and striving to continuously raise food standards and by creating a culture of excellence.

Consumers of today have higher expectations than ever – they rightly expect that their food will be safe and that the information on the label is true. They expect that the FSAI will protect their health and their interests; they trust the FSAI to ensure that the food they purchase and consume is safe, and that a fully functioning food safety system is in place.

As one of the first food safety authorities established in the world, the FSAI has come a long way since 1999. It is a journey that has resulted in the organisation being internationally well regarded and respected for its work and it's people who work in partnership with a food inspectorate and laboratory network throughout the country. Whilst immensely proud of that record, there is a need to continuously strive to raise the bar to ensure we keep pace with an evolving regulatory landscape; rapid innovations in the industry; novel technologies and processes; new and emerging risks and globalisation and lengthening of the food supply chain.

This Strategy sets out our vision, mission, values and strategic goals which will guide us for the period 2016 – 2018. Delivering this Strategy will require working in collaboration with our stakeholders, cooperating with other parts of the Irish and global food safety ecosystem and having access to timely, accurate and relevant information that supports our risk assessment and risk management decisions.

Vital to achieving our Strategy is the incredibly talented team within the FSAI, who are passionate about food safety and committed to delivering on our mission and achieving our vision. I am committed to providing the team with the supports they need to enable them to excel in their roles and to developing our organisation which is true to its values. Critical also to delivering on our Strategy is the food safety inspectorate and the national laboratories within the official agencies and we will work with them to ensure they have the tools and materials required to carry out their enforcement responsibilities.

The FSAI has created a robust, inclusive regulatory framework which has governed and fostered new approaches to ensuring food safety over the last number of years and there is more we can do. Everyone, those in the food sector and the regulatory system and indeed consumers, have a role to play in raising food standards and creating a culture of excellence. The delivery of our new Strategy will build on the work undertaken in the past and will further foster a partnership approach by delivering a strategically planned food safety regulatory system that continues to be relevant, progressive and robust for the future.

I would like to thank the many stakeholders who gave us their feedback during the consultation on our new Strategy and I assure you that your views have been taken on board. The team in the FSAI looks forward to working in partnership with all those in the food safety community to support us in achieving our goals over the coming three years.

Dr Pamela Byrne
Chief Executive

Vision

Safe and trustworthy food for everyone

Mission

We protect consumers by leading a collaborative food safety community to continuously raise food standards and create a culture of excellence

Values

TEAMWORK

We develop and inspire our people to build a better organisation

INTEGRITY

We are honest, open and independent in all we do

PASSION

We are passionate about protecting consumers

RESPECT

We act with respect and personal responsibility

INNOVATION

We change to do things better in pursuit of excellence

COLLABORATION

We recognise and value our partners

Enablers

OUR PEOPLE

LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE

COMMUNICATION AND ENGAGEMENT

PARTNERSHIPS

TECHNOLOGY AND DATA SHARING

POLITICAL SUPPORT

RESOURCES

Strategic Goals

1 Lead a regulatory culture where everyone is passionate about achieving the highest standards for food

OBJECTIVES

- Provide a framework for regulating food that is strategically planned and reviewed to encompass food safety and integrity, with enforcement that is proportionate, risk-based and effective
- Operate a partnership approach to food regulation that engages with stakeholders and promotes innovative compliance solutions to raise standards
- Strive for a world class official control system that includes effective risk-based measures of performance, is verified through audits and delivers the best outcomes for consumers
- Enhance our analysis, reporting and communication on the outcome of official controls
- Provide resources to our partners through training, advice and consultation

2 Use the best scientific knowledge, evidence and expertise to underpin policy and risk analysis in respect of food safety

OBJECTIVES

- Underpin all decisions and advice with the best independent scientific knowledge, evidence and expertise
- Provide high quality, independent, scientific advice to Government to inform and influence food policy within the areas of food safety, integrity and nutrition
- Provide timely, transparent, evidence-based risk assessments using the best available data and methods
- Lead risk management and risk communication effectively and openly to promote trust and engagement
- Lead in identifying and analysing current and emerging threats to food safety, and where appropriate, to integrity and nutrition including leveraging our partnerships in research, regulation and industry
- Strengthen and develop our engagement with national, European and international food safety, integrity and nutrition partners, as appropriate, to ensure the delivery of robust advice and to underpin decision-making

3 Create an environment where Ireland is a trusted and recognised leader in food safety and integrity

OBJECTIVES

- Communicate openly, effectively and promptly on our work to foster trust and be an advocate for food safety and where appropriate, integrity and nutrition
- Set standards that are practical and recognised globally, and implement a programme to attain those standards
- Work in partnership with consumer advocacy groups to address consumers' needs
- Create a network of leaders to champion food safety and integrity as a cornerstone for the success of the Irish food industry
- Build capacity and capability to allow Ireland to react and deal effectively with any national or international food incident or crisis

4 Develop our organisation with an ethos that is true to our values

OBJECTIVES

- Foster a culture of respect, integrity and humility, which is non-discriminatory and supports equality
- Empower and inspire our team to deliver our work effectively and recognise achievements
- Commitment to better communication, continual improvement, competency development and creating innovative opportunities
- Deliver a robust system of corporate governance to ensure accountability, transparency and public value
- Implement and develop management systems that will enable our team to meet and exceed legal and corporate governance requirements

5 Adopt a digital-first approach to maximise accessibility, efficiency and effectiveness

OBJECTIVES

- Develop intelligent and targeted information systems to improve communication, process workflows and service delivery
- Enhance how we gather and use data to better understand the environment in which we operate and inform decision making
- Further enhance customer accessibility and engagement through the use of technology
- Utilise technology as a foundation for innovation
- Explore Big Data to help us do our job better

Outcomes

We protect consumers by leading a **collaborative** food safety community to continuously **raise food standards** and **create a culture of excellence**

Protect Consumers

- Safer food for everyone
- Accurate food information that can be trusted
- Empowered consumers making informed choices
- Reduced incidents of foodborne illness and reduced exposure to unacceptable risks

Raise Food Standards

- Food businesses are in compliance with food legislation and standards
- Relevant data and information that are accessible, accurate and easy to understand

Our Organisation

- The FSAI is a recognised leader and partner in food safety
- An enthusiastic, innovative and effective team committed to delivering our vision
- An organisation that promotes human rights and equality in our team and with our partners to fulfil our positive public duty
- A customer-centric organisation; anticipating and offering our customers what they need and when they need it

Collaborative Approach

- Food safety as a partnership approach works
- Provision of robust evidence-based scientific information to Government policy makers

Culture of Excellence

- Ireland recognises food safety as a cornerstone for success
- Food safety and integrity are priorities for all food businesses
- Everything connects; people, processes, systems and data

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